

ANTHROPONYMS IN THE EPIC “THE BIRTH OF GURUGLI”, WHICH ARE INCLUDED IN THEIR OWN AND ASSIMILATED LAYER

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ANNOTATION In this article, the lexical composition of the anthroponyms used in the epic “Go‘ro‘g‘lining tug‘ilishi” is analyzed, that is, to which layer they belong.

Key words: anthroponym, real name, non-real name, common nouns...

The epic "Gurugli" is considered one of the ancient monuments of folk oral creativity. The epic of heroism, which is widespread mainly in the peoples of the middle and Middle East, Central Asia and the South Caucasus, is a epic. Epics United into a series were created at different times. The roots of some of them go back one and a half to two thousand years ago. In all versions, the basis of the theme is expressed in the courage of Bahadir Gurugli (in the Central Asian version) or Gooroglu (in the western version), who fights for justice, freedom and the cause of people's happiness.

In the epic” The Birth of Gurugli", one can distinguish the atomic horses, i.e. the anthroponyms, into their own layer and the absorbed layer. We know that proverbial nouns entering the acquired layer come from the transition of a word from another language to our language. The Epic had many variants and summed up different language names, including its use among representatives of different languages. This, of course, gave the epic variety and aesthetic pleasure. In the epic we can meet anthroponyms that are used in different languages. For example: inflected nouns in Arabic, Persian, Tajik and similar languages. Anthroponyms used in the epic:

1. **Anthroponyms included in their own layer as applied in the epic.**

2. **Anthroponyms that are part of the absorption layer used in the epic.**

Anthroponyms included in their own layer as applied in the epic.

The names of this species are pure Turkic (Uzbek) names. For example:

*Marie's land had a Khan named **Qawishti Khan**. **Qawishti Khan** had a son, Toliboy sinchi. He was a man with a lot of memory, intelligence, purity, savvy. [5:3]*

Qavishtikhan-name is a pure Turkic (Uzbek) word, used in the meanings of qavish, union.

Anthroponyms that are part of the absorption layer used in the epic.

- **Anthroponyms borrowed from the Tajik language.**

*Odilkhan had two sons of the Tsar, The eldest was **Uraykhan**, and the youngest was Ahmadbek. [5:3]*

Uraykhan - anthroponym is considered in the Tajik language and means such meanings as punching, punching, pushing through a hand or something.

*Taka Turkman deganyana had a land. In this land, there was a bek boreidi named Zhigalikhan, a son of Zhigalikhan named **Gajdumbek**, a daughter named Bibi Hilol. [5:4]*

Gajdumbek is derived from the root word "gaj", which means curved, bent, crooked in Tajik.

*Now hear the sentence from the city called Zargar: the city of Zargar had a king named **Shahdarkhan**. [5:4]*

Shahdurkhan - the name is derived from the Tajik language, a child born with some kind of excess waist(buttock) on his head. [4:503]

*Even so, **Holmon**'s word did not go out to pasture, it remained the same. [5:38]*

Listed here, the **Holmon** anthroponym is in the Tajik language and is a good-natured, happy, satisfied person.

- **Migratory-anthroponyms borrowed from the salbian language.**

*But the Prince had a sycamore called **Soqim**. [5:38]*

Soqim-the name expresses the meaning of a lazy, dysfunctional person.

- **Anthroponyms borrowed from Pahlavi.**

Hearing this, Rustambek's heart reached the "jiz", walked and reached tikka Bibi Hilol. [5:54]

The **Rustamkhan** - anthroponym is made from the word Raodastan in the "Avesto", a man with a torso, a mighty brave, a fortune teller. [4:354]

- **Anthroponyms borrowed from Arabic.**

Hannon pleases the time of the guest, sitting people, to whom the poet spoke a word, brings to the Horde. [5:103]

Hannon is a devout Arabic word for cheerful, energetic, caring. This is one of the qualities of God. [4:461]

As we can see, the anthroponyms presented in the Epic are formed in names used in different language circles, and this will be one proof that many variants of the Epic are spoken in different languages. In its place, it gave the epic aesthetic pleasure and variety. It should also be noted that many of the anthroponyms used in the epic "The Birth of Gurugli" are made up of anthroponyms, mainly those borrowed from Arabic and Persian-Tajik. The meanings they mean also vary. During our scientific research and research, we will study the names that have mastered and belong to the same layer, as well as subject them to analysis.

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